

THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT SELECTION VARIETIES ON THE CLEANING PROCESS OF COTTON STRUCTURE COMPOSITION

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Abstract: *In this article, experimental work was carried out at an enterprise in the LLC cluster system. It processed Andijan-36, 52-4, China-31, China-29, and 52 selection varieties imported from China, grown in Andijan, and studied the effect of the structural composition of different selection varieties on the ginning process.*

Keywords: *fiber porosity, fiber volumetric mass, cotton fragments, cotton structure composition*

1. INTRODUCTION

Several regulations have been adopted to objectively evaluate new cotton varieties found out by breeders of our republic in terms of morphological, economic and technological indicators of their fiber, to select them for future expansion, to study the implementation of seed production work in elite farms that primarily reproduce seeds of new and promising cotton varieties, to study the acceptance of seed cotton at cotton ginning plants and cotton receiving points, and to study their separate collection and storage by varieties and generations.

Many researchers have stated that one of the main factors that affects the efficiency of cotton structure ginning is the initial processing of cotton in cotton ginning enterprises.

The cotton structure coefficient was proposed primarily by R.Z. Burnashev and A.E. Lugachev as an indicator of cotton structure as a cleaning object. However, other scientists considered it only as an indicator of the number of cotton fragments.

In fact, it is not true for real cotton since the number of seeds connected by fibers can vary in a given piece of cotton. In the currently available cotton selection varieties, there can be up to 5-9 seeds in a piece of cotton. However, it should be noted that the main element of the cotton piece is a single fiber-coated seed, which consists of a seed with a width of 3-6 mm, a length of 6-9 mm, and a fiber with a length of 29-36 mm, as well as fluff of various lengths. However, in nature, the fibers in the seed are in a dense state, bent in the boll of the cotton, and do not reach their maximum length even during technological processes.

A piece of cotton consisting of 6-9 fiber seeds is stretched as a result of mechanical effects. In the process of separating the seeds, the fibers attached to them can be straightened and lengthened as a result of mechanical effects.

During the drying and cleaning processes, the separated seed fibers can be further reduced in fiber length due to friction on the working surfaces of dryers and cleaners.

The analysis can be concluded that even if the number of cotton pieces and the number of seeds in them are the same, the sizes of the cotton pieces, that is, the fiber surfaces involved in cleaning, may be different. This situation leads to the possibility that the cleaning efficiency of the cleaners may be different even if the value of the coefficient m , which is measured by the ratio of the number of seeds in the cotton to the number of cotton pieces, is the same.

A number of studies focused on the effect of cotton density on cleaning efficiency found that an increase in its value leads to a decrease in cleaning efficiency. The following formula determines cotton density.

The porosity depends on the V_m .

$$V_m = \frac{\pi}{6} d_{\text{экв}}^3 - \left(\frac{T}{1000} \cdot \frac{B_{\text{min}}}{m_b} \cdot \frac{\ell_t}{\delta_b} + \frac{\pi}{6} a_r^2 \ell_r \right) \quad (1)$$

here $d_{\text{экв}}$ - equivalent diameter of a fiber single seed; T - fiber thickness, tex; B_{min} - fiber output; m_n - fibrous single seed mass; m_b - single fiber mass; ℓ_r - fiber length; δ_b - volumetric mass of fiber; a_r, ℓ_r - width and length of the seed, respectively.

(1) The parameters included in the formula are the same for a single batch of cotton. Therefore, the porosity of the fibers V_m It is largely determined by the size of each fiber or the length of the cotton sliver that substitutes for them.

Generally, it is scientifically significant to compare and analyze the structure of machine-picked and hand-picked cotton and their influence on the efficiency of cleaners.

2. METHODS

This article describes the change in the structure of cotton due to technological processes, its optimal preparation for ginning, and how to determine the coefficient that characterizes the structure of cotton. To know that some experiments were conducted in the Chinabad cotton ginning factory.

We used the cotton variety **China-29½** collected by hand and by machine. After passing the cotton ginning machine 2CB-10 and the YXK cleaners, samples were taken, and then the number of seeds as well as cotton fragments were measured three times.

The value of the coefficient was calculated by this formula:

$$m = \frac{N}{M} \quad (2)$$

Here N - number of single fiber-coated seeds; M - number of cotton fragments.

3. RESULTS

Results of experiments are provided in the first table. Moisture of cotton collected by hand accounts for 10.3% and moisture of cotton collected by machine accounts for 13.1%.

1-table

Change in the cotton structure due to the technological process

No.	Spot from where the sample	Number of fiber-coated seeds in cotton									M	N	m
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9			

was taken													
Hand-picked cotton													
1.	From the cotton heap	25	13	14	14	13	15	20	13	-	127	534	4,2
2.	After 2СБ-10	62	92	16	8	16	9	13	9	-	225	531	2.36
3.	After YXK	330	40	7	9	7	3	3	2	-	401	517	1,29
Machine-picked cotton													
1.	From the cotton heap	80	30	12	10	11	15	13	5	-	176	492	2,8
2.	After 2СБ-10	125	55	10	40	9	10	4	-	-	253	558	2,21
3.	After YXK	470	34	7	9	4	6	4	-	-	534	679	1,27

From the results of the study, it is clear that cotton is separated into small pieces after passing through pneumatic transport, the drying drum of 2СБ-10, and the cleaning flow of YXK. Therefore, the number of single fiber-coated seeds increases, leading to an increased number of cotton fragments. With the hand picking, the value of the coefficient is decreasing from 4.2 to 1.29, and with machine picking, from 2.8 to 1.27. Although the coefficient of cotton's structure with hand-picking and machine picking after the cleaning flow of YXK is almost the same, we can see a significant change in its composition. In particular, the quantity of single fiber-coated seeds picked by hand is 620, while the fiber-coated seeds picked by machine – 125. In addition, the number of double seeds is 92 and 55, respectively. There are other noticeable changes in other parts of cotton.

The registered cases show that previous recommendations of the cotton structure's coefficient did not include the types of cotton picking.

Besides that, the samples of 50g, 100g, and 150g were taken, and after the technological process of the cotton-ginning factory, the number of single fiber-coated seeds in the composition of cotton was obtained. The attained results are provided in tables 2-4 below:

2- table

The quantity of fiber-coated seeds in the 50g of cotton is in the sequence of the technological process of the cotton-ginning plant.

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No.	Spot from where the sample was taken	Cotton composition (number of fiber-coated seeds)									M	N	m
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9			
1.	From the cotton heap	16	6	9	8	3	10	2	7	4	65	268	0.24
2.	At the transfer point	48	15	11	3	6	6	6	5	-	100	271	0.37
3.	After 2 СБ-10	46	25	12	9	2	7	6	2	-	109	278	0.39
4.	After УХК	150	37	9	2	1	2	3	-	-	204	297	0.69
5.	From the gin tray	177	29	12	2	1	1	-	-	-	222	290	0.76

3-table

The quantity of fiber-coated seeds in the 100g of cotton in the sequence of the technological process of the cotton-ginning plant.

T/p	Намуна нуктаси	Cotton composition (number of fiber-coated seeds)									M	N	m
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9			
1.	From the cotton heap	34	17	14	9	12	18	18	7	6	135	550	0.25
2.	At the transfer point	99	33	21	23	7	12	11	5	-	211	544	0.38
3.	After 2 СБ-10	116	41	18	12	9	13	14	5	1	229	570	0.40
4.	After УХК	364	31	12	7	5	3	2	2	3	429	590	0.72
5.	From the gin tray	394	37	16	5	3	3	3	-	-	461	590	0.78

4-table

The quantity of fiber-coated seeds in the 150g of cotton is in the sequence of the technological process of the cotton-ginning plant.

T/p	Намуна нуктаси	Cotton composition (number of fiber-coated seeds)									M	N	m
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9			
1.	From the cotton heap	52	28	11	23	22	22	23	16	5	202	809	0.25
2.	At the transfer point	125	49	31	24	15	9	20	14	5	292	838	0.35
3.	After 2 СБ-10	187	67	16	23	14	20	8	10	1	340	784	0.43
4.	After УХК	489	52	23	14	8	5	8	1	2	602	870	0.69
5.	From the gin tray	548	81	18	7	14	2	-	-	-	670	874	0.77

Based on the results of the study in pictures 3.7-3.9 show histograms of the change in quantity of single fiber-coated seeds, of cotton fragments, and the change of coefficient that determines the cotton

structure in cotton samples of different weights during the technological process of the cotton-ginning factory.

Sequence of technological process

-50g sample ; -100g sample; -150g

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1-picture. The number of fiber-coated seeds in cotton samples of different weights during the technological process of the cotton-ginning factor.

Sequence of technological process

-50g sample; -100g sample; -150g

2-picture. The number of fiber-coated seeds in cotton samples of different weights during the technological process of the cotton-ginning factor.

Sequence of technological process

-50g sample ; -100g sample; -150g

3-picture. The number of fiber-coated seeds in cotton samples of different weights during the technological process of the cotton-ginning factor.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of the study show that with an increase in the weight of the sample, the number of single fiber-coated seeds and cotton fragments increases in accordance with the number of cotton fibers of different weights in the technological process of the cotton ginning factory, and the coefficient characterizing the structure of cotton is almost the same in all samples.

In conclusion, there is a need to conduct extensive research in connection with the efficiency of ginning to develop a coefficient characterizing the structure of cotton as an object of cleaning.

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